

THE CONCEPT OF PRAGMATICS AND ITS INTERPRETATION IN TRANSLATION STUDY

Soatova Mohinur Majid qizi

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Among the latest achievements in the fields of science and technology in the developed countries of the world, in the reforms carried out in our country, "Training of modern personnel who know several foreign languages, carrying out scientific work on foreign languages, improving the methodology of language teaching" is defined as one of the priority tasks. implementation of adequate translations to inform the youth of our country and for this purpose expanding scientific research in the field of translation studies is considered as one of the important issues of today.

The process of translation from Uzbek to English, its specific features, the issues that the translator should pay attention to, the pragmatic features of the original in the translation process and the peculiarities of its restoration in the translation, which can help the translator in his work. aspects and the mistakes it can make are avoided

In each translation process, it goes through two stages as meaning-making sentences and meaning-making words. However, as long as there is no cross-cultural form of speech activity, there will be pragmatic problems of translation for the translator

Accordingly, the translator has to use his universal pragmatic knowledge to deliver the information correctly without any mistakes in the translation. A close study of the speech phenomenon and emotional impact naturally gives rise to several theories of translation, especially the dynamic based on the principle of equivalent effect or action and the "false interpretation" which insists that one should say as it is in the other language. equivalence. Both theories encourage translators to achieve cross-cultural pragmatic success by recognizing that speech acts and events vary across cultures.

However, the semantic features of the original text language, the meanings of words, their use, and their connection with other words create a number of obstacles in achieving pragmatic equivalence in translation.

Translation is the art of re-creation, a high artistic creation, even if it is a creation, it is a creation that requires research, labor, patience, hard work on various

materials . Translation, which is a complex form of human activity, is a creative process of re-creating a speech expression (text) created in one language, preserving its unity of form and content, based on the means of another language. So, the speech expression created using the means of the original language is replaced by such an expression created on the basis of the laws of the translated language. In this way, the substantive and stylistic adequacy of the texts of the original and translation languages is created. The main feature of translation is that it is an art of words. The fact that the word expresses an idea and has the power of influence allows translation to be applied at the level of art.

Summarizing the above, the role and importance of pragmatics in translation is as follows

First, to explain the content of the text written in a foreign language; Secondly, influencing the receptor; this, in turn, can be divided into the following:

- a) Positive impact
 - b) Negative impact
 - c) Neutral
- Thirdly, the correct delivery of certain information; Fourth, defining and studying cultural differences.

Pragmatics not only describes the cultural difference, but also studies it. It should be remembered that pragmatics is a field that cannot be replaced by translation. But they cannot be completely separated from each other.